

Supplier Optimization at Bosch with Knowledge Graphs and Answer Set Programming

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Abstract. The automotive industry is constantly facing the challenge of optimizing their suppliers to meet customer demands while keeping costs low. Knowledge graphs have proven to be effective tools for modeling complex supply chains, but their use for optimization is limited. In this paper, we report on our experience at Bosch to use Answer Set Programming (ASP) to optimize component suppliers in the automotive industry based on knowledge graphs. Evaluation on industrial products shows both efficiency and effectiveness of our modeling framework in generating optimal solutions for supply chain management problems.

1 Introduction

Supplier Optimization. The challenge of *supplier optimization* in the automotive industry concerns identifying the best suppliers for automotive parts and components based on various criteria, *e.g.* quality, reliability, cost, and delivery time. Usually the production of a single system relies on a large number of suppliers providing various parts and components. Managing relationships with a large network of suppliers is time-consuming and resource-intensive. Therefore, supplier optimization is essential to ensure the timely delivery of high-quality components at a competitive cost.

Supply Chain Knowledge Graph. Following our semantic driven strategy [7], we rely on semantic technologies for solving the supplier optimization problem. More specifically, we represent the suppliers and their products (i.e., characteristics, such as the price, quality, lead time, delivery options, certifications, etc.) in knowledge graphs (KGs) [5]. The supplier graph is integrated with the KG representing the bill of materials (BOM), i.e., the components and materials needed for product manufacturing.

Answer Set Programming for Optimization. To compute the optimal set of suppliers, we utilize *answer set programming (ASP)* [3, 4, 6], i.e., a declarative programming paradigm which provides a simple modeling language allowing for a succinct representation of search and optimization problems. Problems are encoded in programs, i.e., finite sets of rules, whose answer sets (which are special models) computed by dedicated ASP solvers, yield the solutions of a problem.

Fig. 1. Architecture overview of the supply chain optimization service.

Approach. In our solution, we utilize the flexibility of KGs and the power of ASP to optimize the suppliers for materials and components of a given product. This problem is particularly challenging due to the large size of the input KG, such that directly invoking ASP on the full data is not feasible. Thus, we develop strategies for extracting only relevant facts required for the optimization. Moreover, to ensure wide usage of our service, we make it accessible also for users without ASP background.

2 Supplier Optimization

Figure 1 describes the overview of the process for using ASP in optimizing suppliers for different parts of a product in the KG. We proceed to describe the required data, e.g. inputs, output, and detail each component, as well as the user experience.

Required Input. To model the supply chain optimization problem, the following components are required: (1) *input facts*, related to the target product. In our use-case, we are working on multiple knowledge graphs, including **supplier KGs**, containing over 4.2M *part-plant-supplier* relationships, along with information about suppliers, such as supplier types (**producer or reseller**), location and carbon footprint; **BOM KGs**, containing a hierarchical structure of the parts of a target product and their current suppliers. Usually a product contains thousands of parts and sub-parts; (2) the *objectives* of the optimization problem, e.g., minimizing the number of suppliers for the product and the total carbon footprint; (3) *constraints*, depending on customers’ requirements, e.g., “avoiding reseller”, ”restrictions on the number of suppliers per part”, etc.

Optimization Process. The process starts with querying the KGs to extract the relevant facts including the product, its parts, as well as current and potential suppliers and defining the optimization objectives, rules and constraints. Then, the retrieved facts, rules, and objectives are compiled into an ASP program [6] by using a simple modeling language. For example, to ensure each part of the product is supplied by one optimal supplier and to minimize the number of optimal suppliers as the most important objective, the following rules are encoded in the program:

```

{{ hasOptimalSupplier(X,Y) }} = 1 :- part(X).
#minimize { N@1 : numberOfOptimalSuppliers(N) }.
  
```


Fig. 2. Web interface for the supply chain optimization service.

where `hasOptimalSupplier/2`, `part/1` and `numberOfOptimalSuppliers/1` are used as predicates, and the variables `X`, `Y` and `N` are used to refer to product parts, suppliers and number of optimal suppliers, respectively. We then invoke the state-of-the-art ASP solver `clingo` [4] to compute the solution to the problem, i.e., the set of optimal suppliers for each product, along with the relevant meta information (e.g., number of optimal suppliers or total carbon footprint).

User Experience. To ensure the wide adoption of our tool, we provided our ASP optimization as a webservice (i.e. API) that supports asynchronous interaction, allowing the user to start a new optimization problem, specify the KG, objective and product-specific constraints. The customers are able to interact with the system by including further constraints and preferences in an iterative fashion if the computed solution does not meet their expectations (e.g., exclude or include further potential suppliers), such that the KG with the optimal selection of suppliers is returned to the user. Along with the API, we also provided a simple web interface for users to facilitate the interaction with our tool (Fig. 2).

Optimization Results. We evaluate our optimization service on real industrial products. Table 1 shows the result statistics for an electronic device as an example. With expert knowledge during running the service, we are able to reduce the number of suppliers from 171 to only 3 suppliers with a minimal total carbon footprint of 50 in almost 15 seconds of running time. The optimization process regarding the number of suppliers and total carbon footprint with respect to the running time is also shown in Figure 3.

3 Discussion and Future Work

By providing the described solution, we pave the way towards wide adoption of using KGs and ASP for industrial optimization. As future steps, we are working on enhancing the scalability of the service by exploiting recent extensions of answer set programs with large neighborhood optimization strategies [1, 2]. As part of future work, we plan to improve user experience by automatically learning complex constraints from users' feedback and incorporating them into the ASP program.

Table 1. Sample statistics for the suppliers of a **single** product and the optimization results resulting from the service. (¹ two current suppliers & one new supplier)

Number of product parts	362
Number of current suppliers	171
Number of potential suppliers	3302
Number of optimal suppliers	3¹
Total carbon footprint of current suppliers	44245
Total carbon footprint of optimal suppliers	50

Fig. 3. Results of the optimization process on the sample product.

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